

Optimization of REDIttools Package for investigating RNA Editing in Thousands of human deep sequencing Experiments

T. Flati^a, S. Gioiosa^a, G. Pesole^{a,c}, T. Castrignano^{b1}, E. Picardi^{a,c}

^a*Istituto di Biomembrane, Bioenergetica e Biotecnologie Molecolari, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Bari, Italy*

^b*SCAI, Cineca, Consorzio Interuniversitario di Supercalcolo, Roma, Italy*

^c*Dipartimento di Bioscienze, Biotecnologie e Biofarmaceutica, Università degli Studi di Bari "A. Moro", Bari, Italy*

Abstract

RNA editing is a widespread post-transcriptional mechanism that alters primary RNA sequences through the insertion/ deletion or modification of specific nucleotides. In humans, RNA editing affects nuclear and cytoplasmic transcripts mainly by the deamination of adenosine (A) to inosine (I) through members of ADAR enzymes. A-to-I modifications increase transcriptome and proteome diversity, and contribute in modulating gene expression at RNA level. RNA editing by A-to-I change is prominent in non-coding regions containing Alu repetitive elements, whereas the list of ADAR substrates in protein coding genes is relatively small. RNA editing modifies several human neurotransmitter receptors and plays important roles in modulating their physiology. Indeed, its deregulation has been linked to a variety of human diseases, including neurological and neurodegenerative disorders, as well as cancer.

Current technologies for massive transcriptome sequencing, such as RNASeq, are providing accurate maps of transcriptional dynamics occurring in complex eukaryotic genomes, as the human one, and are facilitating the detection of post-transcriptional RNA editing modifications with unprecedented resolution. However, the computational detection of RNA editing events in RNAseq experiments is quite intensive, requiring the browsing of the human genome, position by position. To investigate RNA editing in very large cohort of RNAseq data, we have developed a novel algorithm called REDIttools2.0. Here, we describe the core algorithm as well as optimization strategies used to efficiently analyze RNA editing in HPC systems.

Introduction

RNA editing is a widespread post-transcriptional phenomenon occurring in a variety of organisms, including prokaryotes, animals, plants and viruses [1]. It generally alters primary RNA sequences through the insertion, deletion or modification of specific nucleotides. RNA editing by base substitution is prominent in plant organelles and especially in mitochondria, where specific cytidines (C) are modified in uridines (U) by deamination. In mammals, and in particular in humans, RNA editing affects nuclear and cytoplasmic transcripts by C-to-U or A-to-I modifications [1]. While the former is carried out by APOBEC (apolipoprotein B mRNA editing enzyme, catalytic polypeptide-like) family of deaminases and only few instances have been described up to now, the latter is mediated by members of adenosine deaminase that acts on RNA (ADAR) family, and numerous events have been reported in both coding and non-coding transcript regions [2],[3]. ADAR enzymes perform the adenosine deamination in double stranded (ds) RNAs by means of dsRNA binding domains (dsRDBs) and a conserved C-terminal catalytic domain [3],[4]. In humans, three ADAR genes have been characterized, ADAR1 and ADAR2

¹ Corresponding author. t.castrignano@cineca.it

expressed in most tissues and ADAR3 found exclusively in the nervous central system, although its activity has not been yet demonstrated [3]. Since inosine is commonly interpreted as guanosine by translation and splicing machineries, other than sequencing enzymes, A-to-I modifications can alter codon identity or base-pairing interactions within higher-order RNA structures. As a result, A-to-I RNA editing can increase proteome diversity or regulate gene expression at the RNA level [3], [5]. Moreover, editing within pre-mRNAs can generate or destroy splice sites, modulate alternative splicing and influence the dynamics of constitutive splice sites [6]. A peculiarity of RNA editing is that both the edited and unedited versions of affected transcripts are co-expressed in the same cell and the ratio between the unedited and edited variants can be regulated by a variety of factors, depending on tissue type or developmental stage.

A-to-I alterations occur prominently in human brain and in non-coding regions, whereas the list of ADAR substrates in protein coding genes is relatively small. The best studied editing events in coding RNAs are those related to neurotransmitter receptors, such as the glutamate receptor subunit B (GluR-B), and the serotonin 2C receptor (5-HT_{2c}R). In GluR-B two editing sites lead to amino acid substitution with functional consequences. Editing at R/G site regulates the desensitization kinetics of the receptor, whereas the Q/R site regulates the Ca⁺⁺ permeability of the ion channel. R/G site editing affects the nucleotide at position -2 of the 5' splice site of the exon 13 and influences mutually exclusive flop and flip incorporation of exon 14 and exon 15, respectively. Editing at human neurotransmitter receptors has serious physiological implications [7], [8]. Indeed, its deregulation has been linked to several nervous and neurodegenerative diseases, such as epilepsy, schizophrenia, depression, Alzheimer and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis [9], [10]. In addition, the functional importance of this mechanism was established by showing that mice lacking ADARs die in utero or soon after weaning. Recently, editing alterations have also been associated to a variety of human cancers [11], [12]. Under editing at GluR-B Q/R site, for instance, is implicated in malignant gliomas [13]. In addition, RNA editing events can also occur in mature microRNAs and corresponding precursors influencing every step in the miRNA pathway [14], [15].

Current technologies for massive transcriptome sequencing such as RNA-Seq (sequencing of entire transcriptomes) are providing accurate maps of transcriptional dynamics occurring in complex eukaryotic genomes, such as in human's [16], facilitating the detection of post-transcriptional RNA editing modifications [17]. Recently, we have profiled RNA editing in six human tissues (brain, lung, liver, kidney, heart and muscle) from three different individuals using strand-oriented RNA-seq reads generated by a HiSeq2500 Illumina sequencer. Our survey revealed 3,041,422 events, representing the largest collection of A-to-I RNA editing in human, with more than 2 millions of novel positions. Of these, 97% was in repetitive regions and ~90% in Alu elements. Only a limited amount of sites fell in non-repetitive regions (3%), as expected [17]. The number of predicted A-to-I events varied greatly among samples because of sequencing depth variation, stringent filters used to recover editing candidates, and tissue specific roles of RNA editing. Regarding the impact on known human protein-coding genes, we discovered that 13062 loci over a total of 20173 (65%) underwent RNA editing in their exons and/or introns. Very interestingly, we found that edited genes were consistently enriched in genes involved in neurological disorders and cancer. In addition, 74% (1842/2501) of essential genes were in the edited set, confirming the relevant biological role of RNA editing in human genome.

Despite the importance of RNA editing in modulating gene expression and maintaining a correct cellular homeostasis, the A-to-I landscape in human is still incomplete and main biological roles are yet elusive. Our large collection is the tip of the iceberg since it is based on a limited number of human samples, tissues and experimental conditions [17]. Next generation sequencing and, in particular, the deep sequencing of whole transcriptome (RNAseq), is the *de facto* methodology to investigate transcriptome dynamics in various conditions. As a consequence, thousands of experiments have been performed and released through public consortia or specialized web archives such as dbGAP (the database of Genotypes and Phenotypes [18]) or SRA (the Sequence Read Archive [19]). They are precious resources to investigate RNA editing in a multiplicity of human tissues, including physiological, or pathological conditions. The Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) consortium, for example, has released a very large collection of RNAseq experiments from multiple human tissues and donors (densely genotyped), allowing the investigation of RNA editing dynamics in 53 healthy body sites from more than 900 individuals: <http://gtexportal.org> [20]. The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA): <https://cancergenome.nih.gov/> [21], instead, provides more than 14,000 cancer cases and 11,100 RNAseq experiments for exploring RNA editing in a multitude of human tumors. In addition, more than 120,000 RNAseq datasets are available through public archives (dbGAP, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gap> and SRA, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>), allowing the investigation of RNA editing in a variety of experimental conditions. The detection of RNA editing sites in RNAseq data can be accomplished using our software, named REDIttools [22], the first dedicated bioinformatics package for this purpose. It has been implemented in the portable Python programming language and employs the Pysam module, a wrapper of widely used SAMtools [23], which includes methods and functions to handle read alignments in SAM/BAM format. REDIttools run on whatever operating systems equipped with Python 2.6 or superior and Pysam module (version 0.9 or superior). They have been extensively tested and are currently used

worldwide to investigate RNA editing in human diseases or profile RNA editing in single cells [24]. While they are memory efficient (2 to 4 GB of RAM are generally sufficient), the identification of RNA editing variants along an entire genome is computationally intensive and time-consuming. Thanks to the PRACE Preparatory Access (proposal ID 2010PA3430) project we have developed a novel REDIttools algorithm that scales quite well with the number of used cores. Hereafter we describe the novel and optimized REDIttools algorithm and provide scaling analysis demonstrating the suitability of our method to uncover RNA editing in very large cohort of RNAseq data through HPC systems. Results of our research could reveal to be crucial to uncover new biological aspects of RNA editing in a variety of tissues and experimental conditions as well as to identify new sources of biomarkers or novel targets for innovative drugs. RNA editing is yet an under-investigated phenomenon, and little is known about its impact in healthy human tissue or its involvement in diseases. We plan to provide the first and comprehensive catalogue of RNA editing in humans, in order to assay the relationship between editing dysregulation and disease.

Results

The former implementation of REDIttools was based on *Pysam*, one of the well-known Python libraries used to process bam and fastq files [23]. *Pysam*, in turn, is a Python interface of the *htslib* C library which has been designed for efficiently performing operations on genomic data files (e.g., accessing, extracting, piling reads and so on). The algorithm of REDIttools was mainly serial and based on the *mpileup* function of *Pysam* module. Through such function aligned reads were explored, position by position, along the entire genome (see Figure 1). During the traversal of the reference genome the *mpileup* function was naively invoked for each position and independently. It actually did not take into account all previous invocations and for adjacent positions needed to load the same pool of reads from disk as many times as the length of the reads, increasing dramatically the global computational time. In typical RNAseq experiments, REDIttools took on average from 100 to 300 hours to complete in a standard machine (e.g., using only a single core and 2GB of RAM).

Part of the computing time was saved by a multithreaded approach in which the entire genome was split in equal genomic intervals and REDIttools was launched for each individual chunk. Although a modest speed up, intervals required computational times proportional to the read density of the chunk. Therefore, genomic intervals with high read density greatly slowed down the complete analysis. Through the PRACE Preparatory Access (proposal ID 2010PA3430) project we have rewritten the main REDIttools algorithm improving the loading of reads during the traversal of the reference genome and optimizing the handling of genomic intervals in order to employ the parallelization over a high number of cores in dedicated HPC infrastructures. Novel algorithmic solutions implemented in REDIttools are described in detail below.

Figure 1: BAM traversal in the serial version of REDIttools.

Improvement of reads loading from disk. To optimize the loading of sequences from disk, we have modified the code in order to read each sequence only a time, keeping its structure in memory until the end (according to its genome alignment). During the execution, the program loads and keeps all sequences intersecting the current scanned position. As the traversal advances one step further, the set of reads is updated loading new aligned sequences overlapping the current genomic position. Reads no more in overlap are dynamically discarded. In Figure 2, we show a graphical overview of the novel algorithm on a small genomic interval. Initially, no reads are loaded (first position). At the second position only reads with ID 1 and 3 are loaded; at the third position reads with ID 1 and 3 are kept in memory while only the read with ID 2 is loaded. Finally, at position 4 no additionally reads are loaded. Our algorithm is based on the fact that aligned reads need to be traversed sequentially, while

advanced tools such as Pysam (and the *mpileup* function) are optimized for random access and require indexed bam files.

This algorithmic solution yielded the optimized code a tenfold improvement in performance, when compared to the previous implementation.

Figure 2: Improvement of read loading from disk. The same read is loaded from disk only once and stored in memory till the end of its alignment

Optimization of genomic intervals. The initial release of REDIttools allowed multi-core (single-node) analyses through the selection of the number of threads to use. Depending on the number of available threads, genomic intervals were calculated by dividing the whole genome in chunks of equal size and each chunk was assigned to a given thread. According to this strategy, REDIttools treated equally different chromosomal regions. However, expression data do not exhibit a constant coverage and, thus, the number of reads per genomic unit (density of mapped reads) is quite variable. As a consequence, REDIttools took a lot of computational time in high-density genomic regions, slowing down the program execution (Figure 3). It means that the initial multi-threading strategy implemented in REDIttools was not completely satisfactory. Indeed, the algorithm did not scale on multi-node platforms (such as those available at CINECA) and equal-size genomic intervals did not guarantee constant processing time (because of the variable read density), causing a single thread to monopolize the entire time slice allocated to the job (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Equal size genomic intervals.

The optimal interval division (e.g., the one which leads to the best overall execution time) should guarantee an approximately uniform workload and, thus, a balanced set of n intervals $D = \{I_k \mid T(I_1) = T(I_2) = \dots = T(I_n)\}$. This means that if we denote with T_G the total time requested to analyze the input data serially, the time for each k interval will be $T_k = \frac{T_G}{n}$. The crucial aspect is to find a function that predicts the execution time of an interval. For this, we defined the weight of an interval as follows:

$$T(i) = w(i)$$

$$T_I = \sum_{i \in I} T(i)$$

where w is an *ad hoc* function assigning a specific value to each genomic position. We tested several weight functions, including constant, linear and polynomial functions. Thanks to a small test set, we experimentally found that the average read density of genomic intervals correlated best with the computing time in a cubic manner (i.e., $w = cov_i^3$ where cov_i is the coverage at position i).

Figure 4: Dynamic genomic intervals.

To find the function that optimally models the computing time needed to analyze a given interval, we selected a random sample of 1,000 equal-size intervals uniformly distributed across the 24 human chromosomes, in order to take into account also small chromosomes such as the mitochondrial genome (16,571 bp). For each interval, we extracted the average interval coverage (defined as the average number of aligned reads per genomic region) and launched REDIttools (Figure 4). In Figure 5 we display the execution time for each interval. In the plot (in log scale), a given (x, y) point indicates that an interval having average coverage e^x has been analyzed in e^y seconds.

Figure 5: Log-log plot of execution time per interval: each (x, y) point indicates that it took e^y seconds to analyze an interval having average coverage e^x

In addition, the plot includes also a blue curve which is the best cubic equation which interpolates the points in the graph, suggesting that the average time to elaborate a given interval is correlated to its mean coverage. We thus weighted each position with the cube of the coverage and divided the whole genome in intervals such that the overall weights (calculated as the sum of the single-position weights) were approximately equal. In order to preserve the load balance across cores we decided to divide the genome into n equal intervals (where n is the number of cores available during the experiment) and then to split intervals whose weight exceeded $\frac{T_G}{n}$ (where T_G is the weight for the whole genome).

Parallel implementation. REDIttools are not natively parallel. It means that researchers can run REDIttools as a normal Python executable in a classic serial fashion. The parallel version of REDIttools, instead, has been implemented by means of an *ad-hoc* MPI script written in Python. We exploited mpi4py [25], a Python library which provides binding of the Message Passing Interface (MPI) standard for the Python programming language. Thanks to mpi4py, it is possible to exploit multiple computing nodes by means of collective communication primitives (e.g., send/receive, scatter/gather, etc.). In our case a simple master/slave template is sufficient for coordinating the overall computation.

The layout of the computation is reported in Figure 6. Starting from a BAM file and a coverage text file, the program runs n processes in parallel, writing a single output file per each process.

Figure 6: Layout of REDIttools parallel analysis tool. The interval assignment and processing in an MPI environment is regulated by a master process which dispatches new intervals as new slave processes become available.

To produce the coverage file, we loaded the samtools executables and launched the command `'samtools depth bamfile'`, where *bamfile* is the input file; we then split the file into chromosomes for an easier subsequent access. When the MPI script starts, there are n MPI processes available for computation. Among all the MPI processes, one is chosen and assigned as master: the master has the task of distributing the work to other processes and collecting results. All the remaining MPI processes are considered to be slave processes and their goal is to wait for the master to send data to be processed and return results to the master when the computation has been completed. The master can assign new jobs as processes become available.

In Figure 6, for example, the first slave is assigned to the first genomic interval (i.e., the one identified by coordinates chr1:1-2M). As the analysis of this interval is completed, the slave process notifies this event to the master which might assign it a new job if there are still intervals to be analyzed. At the end of each interval computation, each slave process outputs a single file in output containing the information for that interval. An example of output returned by REDIttools is reported in Figure 7.

Region	Position	Reference	Strand	Coverage-q25	MeanQ	BaseCount[A,C,G,T]	AllSubs	Frequency
chr21	15412990	A	1	18	37.22	[3, 0, 15, 0]	AG	0.83
chr21	15415901	A	1	13	37.15	[2, 0, 11, 0]	AG	0.85
chr21	15423330	A	1	11	38.27	[4, 0, 7, 0]	AG	0.64
chr21	15425640	A	1	8	36.12	[0, 0, 8, 0]	AG	1.00
chr21	15456434	T	1	90	34.96	[0, 6, 1, 83]	TC TG	0.07
chr21	15461406	A	1	83	37.27	[73, 0, 10, 0]	AG	0.12
chr21	15461417	A	1	90	36.26	[72, 0, 18, 0]	AG	0.20
chr21	15461444	A	1	64	37.22	[26, 0, 38, 0]	AG	0.59
chr21	15461479	A	1	70	36.96	[66, 0, 4, 0]	AG	0.06
chr21	15461486	A	1	68	37.06	[61, 0, 7, 0]	AG	0.10
chr21	15461503	A	1	76	37.26	[69, 0, 7, 0]	AG	0.09
chr21	15461511	A	1	81	37.68	[55, 0, 26, 0]	AG	0.32

Figure 7: Excerpt of the output of REDIttools on chromosome 21. Statistics such as coverage, mean quality and nucleotide distribution are reported at a site-by-site level.

Strong Scaling analysis. We evaluated the scalability of our optimized REDIttools version on the Marconi HPC infrastructure (Tier-0 cluster) at CINECA using 540/1,080/2,160 and 4,320 cores. All experiments were conducted on the KNL partition of Marconi. Figure 8 plots the elapsed time (in seconds) needed to analyze a single sample when using an increasing number of cores. The blue line represents the recorded time for the REDIttools algorithm, while the red line shows the ideal-scaling behavior. For example, REDIttools took 3,132 seconds using 540 cores, while it took only 2,103 seconds when the number of cores doubled (while the optimal should be 1,566 seconds). In Figure 9 we also report the speedup factor related to the number of used cores. As expected, the algorithm scales adequately with the increasing number of used cores, even though a performance decay is evident when too many processors are used. This trend may be due to the network messages exchanged between the MPI processes, to sub-optimal intervals (increasing the number of cores the extent of genomic intervals decreases and the read density is difficult to be calculated accurately) or to Amdahl's law.

Figure 8: Execution time with varying number of cores.

Figure 9: Speed up in function of the number of cores used during the computation.

Weak Scaling analysis.

The weak scaling analysis of our algorithm has not been performed since it is strongly CPU-bound and not memory-bound. In contrast with application domains in which data can easily be multiplied (e.g., volume molecular dynamics analyses), our data cannot absolutely be divided into equal-size sub-problems, due to the highly variable read density over genomic regions. Indeed, a given thread might well dramatically slow down on high-density intervals.

Conclusions and future work

Scaling analyses on real RNAseq experiments show that our novel REDIttools version, named REDIttools2.0, is on average ten times faster than the previous implementation and the speed up scales adequately with the number of cores involved in the analysis.

The novel and optimized REDIttools code will be publicly released under MIT license and concurrently with the submission of the main algorithmic manuscript on an international and peer-reviewed journal.

We plan to present results of REDIttools2.0 at National and International Congresses focusing on bioinformatics and computational biology as well as at PRACEdays as an example of bioinformatics application for the analysis of Big Data.

We also plan to publish the main algorithm in international peer-reviewed journals taking into account: 1) the optimized REDIttools version and 2) the impact of RNA editing in humans.

Future work includes the analysis of RNA editing on large transcriptome datasets (>10,000 samples) like those produced in GTEx or TCGA projects, providing the opportunity to decipher the real biological role of RNA editing in human and facilitating the medical research in finding new prognostic targets or in developing novel and innovative drugs for the incoming “genomic surgery”.

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